

University Of Duhok
School Of Basic Education
English Department

USING STORYTELLING AS A PRACTICAL APPROACH IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

By:

Ahlan Salih Muhammad Sharif

Hoshang Farooq Sabri

Supervised by:

Mrs. Shaima Ahmed Hasan

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Abstract

Teaching English, especially for children who are in primary schools should be enjoyable, interesting, repetitive, and understandable. In doing so, there should be appropriated methods for teaching English to them. One of the alternative methods is that can be applied in the classroom is called Total Physical Response.

TPR is one of the English teaching approaches and methods developed by Dr. James Asher (1977). This method attempts to center the attention to encouraging learners to listen and respond to the spoken target language commands of their teachers.

TPR is a language teaching methods build around the coordination of speech and action. It attempts to teach language through physical activity. This method tries to introduce some language skills or components in an action in which a teacher serves three roles: an order taker, a model provider, and an action monitor in which learners serves as models and action performers while they feel ready to speak out.

Keywords: Teaching English, primary schools, TPR, James Asher

Dedication

In everything we do in our lives we need some guidance and support from elders, especially those who are very close to our heart.

First of all, we thank our God for giving us this power and ability to accomplish this work.

This humble work is dedicated to our sweet and loving

Parents, whose affection, love, encouragement and prays of day and night make us able to get such success and honor.

Along with all hard working and respected **Teachers**

And we dedicate this work to our precious and brave **Peshmergas** who are now in fronts defending of our country and to the soul of our glorious martyrs that always devoted their lives to make a shiny future to our nation.

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Ahlam Salih

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1.1 An overview of method of teaching and storytelling

Many years ago, during the mid1880s to mid1980s, the language teaching had been involved in a search, that search seeking for general something called Methods. This method's widely difference according to told system in the classroom and depend on the audiences. Historically it describes a succession. In this research we will try to show the principle of the Method during story telling in primary schools. Edward Anthony (1963) has demonstrated that the method concept was the second of hierarchical elements Approach and Technique. The method has defined as an overall plan for systematic presentation of language based upon a selected approach. Nowadays, this definition has been used as a common tool among linguistic teachers, also Richard and Rodgers (1982, 1986) has been shown a reformulation of the concept of Anthony's method, they described method as 'an umbrella term for the specification and interrelation of theory and practice' (1982:154). Through their reformulation of the Anthony's concept they have produced two principal contributions to our understanding of the concept of method:

1. They specified the necessary elements of language-teaching designs that had heretofore been left somewhat vague.

2. They gave us into at last relinquishing the notion that separate definable, discrete methods are the essential building blocks of methodology. By helping us to think in terms of an approach that undergirds our language designs (curricula), which are realized by various procedures (techniques), we could see those methods, as we still use and understand the term, are too restrictive, too pre-programmed, and too 'pre-packaged'. Nearly all language-teaching methods make the oversimplified assumption that what teachers "do" in the classroom can be conventionalized into a set of procedures that fit all contexts. (Brown, 2001, p. 14-15).

The approaches to teach English as a second language:

1. The Grammar Translation Method

The grammar translation method is not current. It has had diverse names. But it has been utilized by language teachers for many years. Before, it was called as a classical method, because it was exploited in the teaching of the classical language. As Latin and Greek (Chastin 1998). Earlier in this century this kind of method was utilized for the intention of serving students to read and know the value of the foreign language literature. It was hoped that through learning the grammar of target language students will be more associate with their native language and this will help them to improve their written & speaking in their native language . Also

learning foreign language help students to be improved intellectually .(Larsen – freeman, P .11)

2. Direct Method

The direct method it is another method which used to be taught for learning a foreign language. The direct method is not recent as the grammar translation method. The main aim of teaching a foreign language was to learn how to communicate at that time this direct method became popular and method. In this method no translation is permitted that is an essential rule in direct method. The direct method takes its name from the fact meaning is to be transported directly during the use of target language. (Larsen – Freeman. P. 23).

3. The Audio-lingual Method (ALM)

Audio-lingual method is a style of teaching exploited in teaching foreign languages. To study and teach the ALM is essential. Because during the World War II this method progressed and became popular. This approach to language learning was like to another method called Direct method. The same as direct method the ALM informed that students to be taught a language directly which means learning a new word or grammar in the target language by avoiding native language. Despite this unlike the direct method the ALM did not concentrate on

teaching vocabulary, on the contrary the teacher drilled students in the use of grammar. According to 'The word 'audio' means something that deals with hearing or listening. It needs ear to listen utterances. Lingual means language that needs reading and practice to get it'.

(Smith 1970: p. 29) (The audio lingual method by Haval Harbi Sulaiman. English department. Evening class. 2014).

4. Suggestopedia

Is a method created by Bulgarian Psychiatrist-educator Georgi Lozanov. Suggestopedia is precise state of learning recommendation obtained from Suggestology that mark out by Lozanov as a 'science...concerned with the systematic study of the nonrational and /or nonconscious influences'. Using music and musical rhythm is the most noticeable feature for learning suggestopedia. The most features of suggestopedia are the decoration, furniture, arrangement of the classroom, the use of music, and the authoritative behavior of the teacher.(Richard & Rodgers, 2003,p .100)

5. The silent way

It is the name of another method which organized by Caleb Cattengo. It is established on introducing that the teacher should be silent as much as possible in

the classroom but assimilator should be advocated to bring forth as much language as possible. Factors of the silent way, specially use of color charts-series of colorful wall charts. The rods were used to introduce vocabulary (colors, numbers, adjective (long –short) verbs (give-take, pick up). (Richard & Rodgers , 2003, p.81).

6. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)

The commencements of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) can be found in the changes in the British language teaching tradition period in the late 1960s. Until then, Situational language teaching represented the basic British approach to teaching English as a foreign language. In Situational Language Teaching, language was taught by using basic frameworks in meaningful situation-based activities. But as the linguist theory latent Audiolingualism came from the United States in the mid-1960s, British applied linguistics began to call into question the hypothetical suppositions underlying Situational Language Teaching:

The American well-known linguist Noam Chomsky graded at structural linguistic theory in his book “Syntactic Structures” (1957). Chomsky showed that the current standard structural theories of language were unable in depending on basic features of the language creativity and the singularity of individual sentences. And British applied linguistics underlined another basic dimension of language that was not

addressed enough in approaches to language teaching at that time the functional and communicative prospect of language. They saw the necessity of focusing on the language teaching on communicative skill rather than on mere mastery of structures. Scholars who were the supporters of this view of language, such as Christopher Candlin and Henry Widdowson, focused on the works of British functional linguists (e.g., John Firth, M. A. K. Halliday), American work in sociolinguistics (e.g., Dell Hymes, John Gumphez, and William Labov), in addition of the work of philosophy (e.g., John Austin and John Searle).

There is another impulsion for different approaches to foreign language teaching that came from changing educational realities in Europe. When many European countries gained their independence, it was a need to teach adults the major languages of the European Common Market. The European commission, a regional organization for cultural and educational cooperation, examined the problem. So the European Council focused majorly on this area. It created international conferences on language teaching, they published books about language teaching, and it had a great role in increasing the formation of the international confederation of applied linguistics. Developing alternative methods of language teaching was their major priority. (Richards & Rodgers, 2003, P.153)

7. The Natural Approach

There are many speculations about learning second language acquisition which being negotiated and warmly argued for many years (Krashen1982-1997). The main theoretical branch of Krashen perspectives was demonstrated as the Natural Approach , which improved by one of his friends, Tracy Terrell. They both believed defraying production can be beneficial for a child till appearing spoken language that the pupil have to feel as unwind as possible in the school, he/she should be exposed to amount of communication and acquisition. Indeed, the natural approach demands to put the TPR assignments into work at initial stages of language learning while an understandable input is necessary to initiate language acquisition. We can find some possible long-term aims in language learning. Second language can be learned in different cases like verbal communication or written communication. In this approach according to Krashen and Terrell the learners go through three phases (1) reproducing phase which involves in improving listening skills. (2) Basic production phase which is spotted by students' mistakes in the process of learning the language. The teacher shouldn't correct the mistakes because in this stage the emphasis goes the meaning not form and correction can be made when it changes the meaning fully. (3) The final stage consists of expanding production which includes complicated games, playing

roles, acting and dialogues and small groups in expansion. The main aim of this stage is to improve speaking ability. Therefore, the teachers needed to be very wide in correcting mistakes. (Brown, 200, p.31)

8. Total Physical Response (TPR)

TPR is a language teaching method built around the coordination of speech and action it attempts to teach language through physical activity. It produced by James Asher (1977). Nowadays TPR which is a household word among language teachers .It connected a number of other insights in its rationale. In child language Asher (1977) showed that the child learning in their first language, seems to be a huge lessons before they speak their listening is accompanied with their physical responses (reaching, grabbing, moving, looking, and so on). TPR difficulty used the imperative mood, however into more professional levels. Commands were an easy way to motivate learners to move around and to loosen up: close the door, sit down) The verbal response was not important. TPR it seemed to be effective especially in the beginning levels of language proficiency. In a TPR classroom, when students overcame the fear of speaking out, classroom conversations and other activities proceeded as in nearly any other communicative language classroom. In TPR reading and writing activities, students are limited to spinning

off from the oral work in the classroom. (Brown,2001,p.29-30) Finally for increase our understanding of Total Physical Response we will turn to some Questions:

1. What are the goals of teachers who use TPR?

Teachers who use TPR believe in the importance of having their students enjoy their experience in learning to communicate in a foreign language and to reduce the stress of the students.

2. What is the role of the teacher? What is the role of the students?

The teacher is the director of all student behavior. The students are the imitator of teacher's nonverbal model.

3. How are the feelings of students dealt with?

One of the main reasons TPR developed to reduce the stress of students. One of the primary ways is to allow students to speak when they are ready, because forcing the students will create anxiety. Also, when students begin to speak, perfection should not be expected. Another way to relieve anxiety is to make language learning enjoyable either by using zany commands or humorous skits. Finally, it is important that there not be too much modeling.

4. How is evaluation accomplished?

Teachers will know immediately whether or not students understand by observing their student's actions. Formal evaluation can be conducted simply by commanding individual students to perform a series of actions. As the students become more advanced, their performance of skits they have created can become the basis for evaluation.

5. How does the teacher respond to student errors?

Surely when at the beginning the students are speaking they will make errors. Teachers should be tolerant of them and only correct major errors. (Larsen-freeman, 2003, pp.113, 114, 115)

1.2 Theories of TPR:

1- Vladimir Propp's theory (Propp 1928), says that story (especially folktale) has three stages, which are, Peaceful home, break-up of the home, sometimes it looks like it caused by a rogue figure, and then the member of the broken home tracks down the rogue by defeating her/him, and rebuilds the home.

2- Joseph Campbell's theory (Campbell 1949), also says that story (especially a heroic legend) has three stages, which are, the heroine/hero's society is boring and

vain, the hero/heroine goes on an adventure, gains a divine object, and returns to the society with the divine object, then reforms the society.

3- Carl Jung's theory of Psychological integration, he also called it "Individuation" (doing things individually), and says that stories have two stages, which are, elements are integrated, and elements are apart.

4- From the 1920s to the 1950s, which was the Golden Age of Modern Western Drama, "The Well –Made Play" was well-known, this form was applied to other forms of storytelling, such as novels and screenplays. This theory claims that stories are revolved with the conflict, like, exposition, conflict develops, crisis, and resolution.

5- Aristotle, the ancient Greek philosopher, and drama and literary critic, he discussed the theory of "Catharsis".

This was applied only on the one sort of drama, which is "Tragedy", in which the hero is damaged by his own fault. According to "Catharsis", the audience feels panic, and finally they release and relax, by knowing the person who causes.

The storytelling structure of primary school classroom

TPR Storytelling divides its lessons into five steps, each of which progress the learners to more challenging and meaningful uses of the target items of the day. First step, the TPR has been used by teachers in the schools to give the same words daily. After pupils they have been gotten those words and related actions they have been gotten and comprehensive input of vocabulary in such practice by using gestures, manipulative, pictures and familiar vocabulary. After that the practical part of TPR started with some commands pupils act out a scenario while the teacher narrates it. Second step, when the pupils have been learned vocabulary words via TPR practice and scenario, the class divides pupils into two pairs equally in order to drill of producing the words, one pupil in pair reads the word the other pupil gives the corresponding gesture. Then they exchange their roles. After that one pupil gives the gesture and the other one responding the word. Third step, using pictures from the text then the teacher narrates a mini-story involving the targeted vocabulary words. When the story is internalized pupils then recite it to their partner. The pupils have to tell the story from memory or illustrations words written on the board as prompt. The class then meets again and pupils volunteers retell the story to the other students to perform it. Also, the teacher may help the class by changing a few details about plot or characters to create a new revision to the original story line. Fourth step, mini-stories are contrived by the teacher to

prepare pupils to narrate, read and write longer story that utilizes the vocabulary from the mini-stories. After the whole group of mini-stories has been overcome by the class, then the teacher repeats the third step to introduce the longer story. When this story has been presented and acted out. Similar with mini-stories pupils build upon the longer story utilizing their existing language experience to decorate the plot personalize the characters, and create revisions. The final step the teacher then gives pupils chances to take advantage on their creativity by writing, illustrating, performing, and sharing their own original stories. Further activities the teacher may hope to include: drama, creative writing, creating studying booklet, contests, and group/pair work...etc. (Ray& Seely, p.24,25).

There are many applications or techniques that teachers use in telling the stories:

According to James J. Asher, one of the ways for applying the storytelling in classrooms is repeating sentence patterns when telling the stories. The teacher will choose story, then telling the story by using the puppets or storytelling pieces, such as pictures of characters and different items that can involve children. The teacher will say a difficult vocabulary within telling the story, by using the puppets or storytelling pieces. Then the teacher will call volunteers to take the puppets and storytelling pieces, and inspiring them according to what the story says. Then when the children are familiar with the story, the teacher will make and give them copies of the storytelling pieces. Then the teacher will be aware of how they will present, read or tell the story very well, so everyone can understand, and at the same time the teacher will choose some children to be guest storytellers and give them all parts of storytelling while the others are doing their job. (David Nunan, 2005)

((Another type is The Class Reading)):

This type is a common application in TPR. The teacher will usually begin the class reading, by reading the story or a part of the story, and then the teacher will ask students to translate it into their mother tongue language. The teacher can help learners by translating some words that they are not familiar with. This translation can be done by the students or the whole students as well. That can help the learners to fully understand the meaning or getting the meaning more accurately. Then the whole class will discuss the reading in target language. Through this discussion the students will fully understand the meaning of the story, and then the teacher may use the pop-up grammar technique, which all grammar points inside the story will be explained very briefly. Then usually the teacher will ask questions about the reading itself, also about the student and their lives.

(http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/TPR_Storytelling#Class_reading)

Issues which come up during story telling:

The problems of storytelling of how stories are performed of who gets tell their story and to whom and how story tellers are heard and understand of why people say and listen to, stories are difficult enough. The performative, social and cultural dimension of storytelling, political and moral powers of storytelling are fraught with complication of voice, authority, interpretation, meaning, action, etc. (J.Covlin , 2000). Furthermore, student who are not used to total physical response which is part of storytelling might face some obstacles, this can be the main point about teacher if he or she prepared to perform the action. The students feel happier about copying, also the students are in a group and do not have to perform for the whole class. It is only really compatible for primary school or for beginner level, while it is obvious that it is far more useful at lower than primary school or lower level since the aimed language brings itself to such activities even though it can successfully be performed at intermediate and advanced levels. In this respect it is necessary to adapt the language accordingly, for example when teaching ways of walking (stumble, stagger, and tiptoe) to an advanced class and cooking verbs to intermediate student (stir and grate), TPR can be employed. It is not capable of change used to teach everything and if used a lot, it would be continual. This method is a fun way of changing the dynamics and pace of lesson used in connection with other methods and instructions or techniques. Also, TPR should be

mixed with others because it needs much energy so that learners do not feel tired of language learning. Although, the use of it in classroom has often been operative it does have its fault, and of this method fault is that when problem in teaching abstract, vocabularies or expression. As a remedy the teacher can write the word on cards with picture if suitable. If the teacher uses it for a long period of time the target language, since TPR is made up of mainly of commands, it tends to neglect narrative description and conversation form of language. (Seni, 2005).

Conclusion

Teaching English for children is very important, particularly for primary schools' classes. In order for this process to be more beneficial, facilitative, pleasant, and interesting, we need to have some essential methods and approaches. For sure there is a great approach which is called Total Physical Response (TPR). Which is made to assort between action and speech, and it's is well-developed and found by James Asher in 1977. This method can help children to learn to speak, write, and communicate in the targeted language in a very best way.

TPR also contains of the Storytelling, which a very significant way to let children learn via using it in classrooms. Using the storytelling as a method for learning new languages can let and assist the children to know a vast number of vocabularies of the targeted language, and it enhances children to understand the vocabularies by using them every day inside the class with in various activities.

In addition of that, children can act the stories, and that storytelling can encourage children to have the desire for working in groups as well.

References

- Bahasa D. S., Tahun 33, No. 2, (2005, August). Teaching children using a TPR method. Hundoyo Puji Widodo. University of Adelaide, South Australia.
- Brown, H. D. (2000). An approach to language pedagogy. *In Teaching by principles*. p. 29-30, 31, 14-15. San Francisco, California.
- Christopher J. C. (2000, December, 4th). The problems of storytelling: Forgotten voices of the Holocaust, volume 1, No. 3. In *Forum: Qualitative social research (FQS)*.
- Davies, A. (2007), *Storytelling in the classroom* Freeman, D. L. (2000). *Techniques and principles in teaching language*, pp.113, 114, 115, 23, 11. New York: Oxford University.
- Miller, E. (2011, January), *Theories of story and storytelling*
- Nunan, D. (2005), *Practical English language teaching*. New York. Richards, J. C. T. S. Rodgers, (2003), *Approaches and methods in language teaching*. P. 81, 153,100. United Kingdom, Cambridge University press.
- Ray & Seely C. (1998) *Fluency through TPR storytelling: achieving real language acquisition in school*, p.24,25

Smith (1970): p. 29) in Sulaiman, H. H. (2014) The audio -lingual method. English department, evening class.

(http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/TPR_Storytelling#Class_reading)